

Cloud Macrostructure and Radiation

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ABSTRACT

Cloud radiative properties are sensitive not only to drop size and other parameters of cloud micro-structure, but also cloud shape, spacing, other parameters of cloud macro-structure. Field programs such as DoE/ARM and DoE/UAV are now underway to improve the measurement and modelling of physical and radiative properties of clouds under a variety of meteorological conditions. A parallel effort is underway to improve cloud remote sensing from current GOES and AVHRR platforms as well as the upcoming NASA suite of EOS instrument which will provide higher spectral and/or spatial resolution, such as MODIS and ETM+/LATI. Corrections to plane-parallel theory to account for cloud inhomogeneity take different forms for the 100 km scale of climate model grids, and for the 1 km scale of typical satellite pixels. A first approximation for grid-scale fluxes is obtained by a linear weighting of clear and cloudy fractions, using an "effective cloud thickness" which depends on the within-cloud variability. A key finding for improving pixel-scale retrievals is that there is a characteristic "radiative smoothing" scale of several hundred meters. This scale has been observed as a change in the spatial spectrum of Landsat cloud radiances, and was also recently found with the help of Spinhirne's lidar at NASA-Goddard, by searching for returns from directions nonparallel to the incident beam. "Offbeam" Lidar returns are now being used to estimate the cloud "Green's function", which will be applied to improving simple IPA estimates of cloud radiative properties. This and other measurements of 3D transfer in clouds, coupled with 3D Monte Carlo transfer methods, are beginning to provide a better understanding of the dependence of radiation on cloud inhomogeneity, and to suggest new retrieval and parameterization algorithms which take account of cloud inhomogeneity.

1. INTRODUCTION

The large-scale terrestrial climate is well-known to be very sensitive to small changes in the average albedo of the earth-atmosphere system. Sensitivity estimates vary, but typically a 10% change in global albedo, with all other quantities held fixed, changes the mean equilibrium surface temperature by 5 °C, more than, say, a doubling of CO₂. [See, for example, Cahalan and Wiscombe, 1993.] Atmospheric absorption also has a profound effect on the climate, through its impact on the intensity of the Hadley circulation and convective processes in general [For example Kiehl et al, 1995]. Current global climate models are beginning to attempt to predict cloud liquid water, and from that the albedo and cloud absorption in each gridbox, rather than simply to adjust the albedo and absorption to what are believed to be observed values, as in the past. The ability of the models to compute the albedo is largely a function of their inability to predict the microphysical and macrophysical statistical properties of cloud liquid water within each gridbox. As Stephens (1985) has emphasized, the mean albedo of each gridbox depends not only on the mean properties of the clouds within each box, but also upon the variability of the clouds, which involves not only the fractional area covered by clouds, but also the cloud structure itself.

The dependence of average albedo and absorption on cloud structure has been found to be particularly striking in the case of marine stratocumulus, a major contributor to net cloud forcing. A study based on the FIRE observations of California

stratocumulus in July 1987 showed that cloud structure has a greater impact on average albedo than does cloud fraction (Cahalan et al, 1994a and 1994b). That study employed a "bounded cascade" model to distribute the cloud liquid, with parameters f and c adjusted to fit the variance of the log(LWP), and the exponent of the power spectrum, respectively. In order to isolate the effects of horizontal liquid water variations on cloud albedo, the usual microphysical parameters were assumed homogeneous, as was the geometrical cloud thickness. In order to simplify comparison with plane-parallel clouds, the area-averaged vertical optical depth was kept fixed at each step of the cascade. The albedo bias was found as an analytic function of the fractal parameter, f , as well as the mean vertical optical thickness, τ_v , and sun angle, θ . For typical values observed in FIRE ($f = 0.5$, $\tau_v = 10$, and $\theta = 60^\circ$) the absolute bias is 0.09, or 15% of the plane-parallel albedo of 0.69.

In the following, we first briefly review plane-parallel biases in cloud albedo and absorption estimated from NASA/FIRE and DoE/ARM field observations; then discuss the "nonlocal independent pixel approximation", or nIPA, which provides a practical alternative to the simple IPA with accuracies often approaching full 3D Monte Carlo in computations of plane-parallel albedo biases, and in the retrieval of cloud properties from satellite radiances; thirdly we show measurements of the "cloud Green's function" used by the nIPA technique, made with a "wide-angle" configuration of the Goddard lidar facility; and finally, we show that under certain commonly-

observed conditions the albedo can be obtained from the plane-parallel albedo by employing a "reduced optical thickness" where the reduction factor increases with cloud variability.

2. PLANE-PARALLEL BIASES

Figure 1 dramatizes the importance of cloud structure in determining cloud albedo. It shows the diurnal cycle of the "plane-parallel albedo bias", namely the bias in plane-parallel estimates of cloud albedo based only on the mean cloud quantities in a given gridbox. The upper curve is the total bias computed with 100% uniform cloud cover, while the lower curve shows "cloud fraction bias", or that portion of the bias found by using the actual diurnally varying cloud fraction, but still treating the clouds as uniform. This cloud fraction bias vanishes at about 11 AM when the cloud fraction is nearly 100%. Yet that is precisely when the total bias is largest (ignoring the sharp rise at sunset, which is an artifact of the computation due to the neglect of surface albedo). The middle curve explains the peak at 11 AM - it is the bias due only to the internal variability of the cloud, namely the "fractal structure bias". That bias is largest when the cloud fraction is largest, because that occurs when the convection is strongest, so that the most extensive clouds are not only thickest, but also most variable. This observation has also been born out by microwave observations of cloud liquid over Porto Santo in the Atlantic Madeira Islands during the June 1992 ASTEX program, and during the year following.

Figure 1. Albedo of a uniformly cloud-covered region minus that of a region 82% uniformly covered (lower curve); albedo of an 82% uniformly covered minus that of a region 82% fractal (middle); and sum (top).

Figure 2. Apparent absorption measured by up and down-looking broadband flux radiometers on high-altitude Egrett and low-altitude Otter aircraft during DoE/ARESE field experiment during September 1995. Vertical axis is net vertical flux divergence (as a percentage of incident flux in each band at the upper aircraft) between 13 km Egrett altitude and 1 km Otter altitude in the near-infrared (red curve, 0.7 to 3.3 microns) and visible (blue curve, 0.2 to 0.7 microns), as measured by up and down-looking hemispheric broadband radiometers onboard the Egrett (at 13 km) and Otter (at 1 km) aircraft near the DoE Southern Great Plains ARM site on October 26, 1995 during the ARESE Intensive Observation Period. The horizontal axis shows both the flight distance and the location of two turns (arrows) with the headings labelled in between (h is measured clockwise from $0 = \text{North}$). The large correlated excursions in both NIR and Vis are due to horizontal fluxes caused by cloud inhomogeneity. To cancel horizontal fluxes between NIR and Vis, a weighted difference $A = \text{NIR} - c \cdot \text{Vis}$ is computed, where c is chosen to minimize the spatial variance, which occurs when $c = \text{linear correlation coefficient of NIR and Vis}$. In this case $c \sim 2/3$, and the resulting values of A are plotted as X's. The mean of A is only slightly reduced from that of NIR, but the variance of A is reduced by nearly a factor of 4!

Figure 2 shows the large excursions in "apparent" absorption observed during the DoE/ARESE field experiment in September 1995. The large excursions even to negative numbers caused by horizontal radiative fluxes, can be eliminated by cancelling them between different bands, as shown here for broadband visible and near-infrared. To minimize the variance of the difference, the linear correlation coefficient "c" is used as a multiplier.

3. NONLOCAL INDEPENDENT PIXEL APPROXIMATION

To correct for the effect of horizontal fluxes on satellite cloud retrievals, we employ the nonlocal IPA, or nIPA (Marshak et al., 1997). This simulates the smoothing effect of horizontal fluxes via a "smoothing kernel". The inverse of the smoothing kernel has the effect of sharpening the distribution of cloud optical thickness and liquid water. Figure 3 shows a comparison of both IPA and NIPA retrievals with the exact but expensive 3D Monte Carlo. The NIPA points show dramatically improved retrievals.

Figure 3. Scatter plot of IPA (red) and NIPA (blue) albedo versus Monte Carlo albedo from a bounded cascade having 77% cloud. NIPA is much faster than Monte Carlo, and much more accurate than IPA.

4. CLOUD GREEN'S FUNCTION

The smoothing in the nIPA approach is accomplished by the cloud radiative Green's function, which is the pattern of reflected (or transmitted) radiation produced by an incident localized beam, such as that of a laser. Most of the reflected light is backscattered in the direction of the incident beam, but the rms distance between the beam and the reflected photons, the "spot size" increases with cloud thickness. An example, (as far as we know the first such) is shown in Figure 4 (Davis et al, 1997a and b). This is the intensity as a function of angle between the incident lidar beam and the detected return photons. Note the characteristic exponential falloff associated with photon diffusion at large angle. Integrating this function

times the squared distance gives the rms distance, shown for

two cloud optical thicknesses.

5. REDUCED THICKNESS

For a range of intermediate mean cloud thicknesses, the

mean albedo can be computed from a "reduced" mean thickness, where the reduction factor is a known function of f , approximately 0.7 when $f = 0.5$. Harshvardhan and Randall suggested that globally cloud liquid must be reduced by approximately 0.3 in order to obtain the correct global albedo. In the fractal bounded cascade model this requires an increase in the fractal parameter to $f = 0.8$, and increases the albedo bias by a factor of 5, presumably due to the contribution of deep convective cloudiness. This approach has been used to improve the ToA fluxes in the ECMWF model (Tiedke, 1996).

6. DISCUSSION

A number of new results on the mesoscale-average albedo and absorptivity of stratocumulus clouds, known to be a major contributor to net cloud forcing, have been obtained by both 3D Monte Carlo and analytic methods, and compared to field observations of cloud albedo and absorption. The "apparent" absorption measured by two aircraft in ARESE, in broadband visible and near-infrared bands, shows large excursions from the mean due to horizontal fluxes. The excursions in different bands are strongly correlated, so that appropriate differences may be defined which are largely unaffected by the horizontal transports. The effect of horizontal transports on cloud retrievals can be approximated with a "smoothing kernel", and its inverse has the effect of sharpening the radiatively smoothed cloud distributions obtained by IPA. The kernel in this nonlocal IPA, or NIPA technique is physically related to the "cloud radiative Green's function", which has recently been measured by off-beam lidar technique, and used to interpret the results in terms of a "radiative smoothing scale" which increases with cloud thickness. Finally, one example of the kind of cloud parameterization provided by fractal cloud studies was shown -- the cloud effective optical thickness, which is a simple function of the variance of the logarithm of the cloud liquid water. Climate models are now beginning to incorporate the effects of such internal variability on cloud optical properties.

7. REFERENCES

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